

Title:

Designing a Personalized AI Agent for Restaurant Recommendation Using Version Spaces and Decision Trees

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Abstract:

This paper proposes a personalized AI agent that assists users in selecting suitable restaurants by learning their preferences through version spaces and decision-tree reasoning. The agent collects user feedback, scrapes web data (Yelp, TripAdvisor APIs), and updates its knowledge base iteratively. The model demonstrates symbolic AI reasoning for real-world decision-making and personalized learning.

Keywords:

Artificial Intelligence, Version Spaces, Knowledge-Based AI, Personalized Agents, Decision Trees

Note:

This paper was originally written as part of the *Knowledge-Based AI (CS 7637)* course at Georgia Institute of Technology and is now being shared publicly for academic reference and citation.

Assignment – 3

KBAI

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Goal: To design an AI agent that can plan a personalized holiday experience.

Briefing: I love to travel the world. The hassle I face is planning the trip. I have to invest so much time on researching perfect hotels to stay, places to eat, attractions to visit and still keeping an eye on the budget! So, why not put this burden on an AI agent that could be way more efficient, resourceful and smarter than a human being?

Description: For any holiday, there are four major parts of the trip. Commuting, hotel stay, places to eat and excursions/attractions to visit. In this paper, I am going to focus on the point 'places to eat'. Being a strict vegetarian and very picky about the food, it always gives me hard time to find appropriate places to eat. Budget, food quality, restaurant ratings, time invested, distance from hotel and many more parameters affect my decision. Once a hotel stay is fixed, I want my AI agent to come up with good suggestions about where I can have my breakfast, lunch & dinner.

Design: This AI agent should be personalized for each user. At start it should be a generic one. It should ask questions to the user to understand his/her preferences. AI agent clearly travels from generalization to specialization. Thus, I think concept of version spaces would be best fit for designing this agent.

Challenge 1: How to know preferences of the user?

At start AI agent does not know about what type of restaurants user likes to eat at. It can start with finite set of varied sample restaurant examples and ask user to check each one and tell if he would like to eat there. Number of samples should be enough to achieve a convergence point between too general choice (I can eat any thing any where) and too specific choice (I can only eat ravioli at Venetian, Vegas).

Let's consider below examples for breakfast options where we have set of answers from the user. Positive example means user would like to eat there and negative example means, user does not want to eat there.

Distance	Restaurant type	Meal type	Veg options?	Price range	AI rating	Example type
Walkable	Inn	Indian	Yes	Cheap	Good	Positive
Walkable	Coffee	English	Yes	Moderate	Bad	Negative

	House	breakfast				
Walkable	Coffee House	American	Yes	Cheap	Good	Positive
Car	Breakfast chain	Mexican	No	Moderate	Good	Negative
Walkable	Inn	Italian	Yes	Expensive	Good	Positive

Let's see how agent can come up with personalized template with use of version spaces.

1. Example 1: (+ve): (Walkable, Inn, Indian, yes, Cheap, Good)

Let G be set of general models and S be set of specific models.

G	$\{ (?, ?, ?, ?, ?) \}$
S	(Walkable, Inn, Indian, yes, Cheap, Good)

2. Example 2: (-ve): (Walkable, Coffee House, English Breakfast, yes, Moderate, Bad)

We need to specialize G to exclude negative example.

G	$\{ (?, Inn, ?, ?, ?), (?, ?, Indian, ?, ?), (?, ?, ?, Cheap, ?), (?, ?, ?, ?, Good) \}$
S	(Walkable, Inn, Indian, yes, Cheap, Good)

3. Example 3: (+ve): (Walkable, Coffee House, American, yes, Cheap, Good)

We need to generalize S to include positive example.

G	$\{ (?, Inn, ?, ?, ?), (?, ?, Indian, ?, ?), (?, ?, ?, Cheap, ?), (?, ?, ?, ?, Good) \}$
S	$\{ (Walkable, ?, ?, yes, Cheap, Good) \}$

Also we need to prune G in order to be consistent with S.

G	{ (?,?,?,?,Cheap,?) , (?,?,?,?,?,Good)}
S	{{(Walkable, ?, ?, yes, Cheap, Good)}}

4. Example 4: (-ve): (Car, Breakfast chain, Mexican, no, Moderate, Good)

We need to specialize G to exclude negative example.

G	{ (?,?,?,?,Cheap,?) , (Walkable,?,?, yes ,?,Good)}
S	{{(Walkable, ?, ?, yes, Cheap, Good)}}

5. Example 5: (+ve): (Walkable, Inn, Italian, yes, Expensive, Good)

We need to prune G in order to be consistent with S.
And we need to generalize S to include positive example.

G	{{(Walkable, ?, ?, yes, Cheap, Good)}}
S	{{(Walkable, ?, ?, yes, Cheap, Good)}}

At this point $G = S$, thus a convergence point has reached and AI agent has got a personalized template. Note that, though I am using just 6 parameters for demonstration, ideally it should be more complex with more parameters in order to get the user preferences as accurate as possible.

We can use frames for knowledge representation. A convergence frame can be represented as below.

Slot	Value
Source location	Hotel of stay
Distance	Walkable

Restaurant type	Any
Food type	Any
Veg options	yes
Price range	Cheap
Agent ratings	Good

**Agent rating is the rating of the restaurant calculated by agent. We will discuss this further in the document.

Challenge 2: How to find the restaurants that match user preferences?

In stage-1 of the application, it is all set up with the personalized templates about hotel choice, travel choice, excursion choice etc. When a user actually wants to use the application, agent needs to apply the templates to actual real time data and choose appropriate options for the user.

Database: I propose of using a web scrapper component to work along with the agent. This web scrapper can make use of developer APIs provided by restaurant reviews sites like [yelp](#) and [trip advisor](#) to find out the restaurants around given location. So at a time, the agent can deal with a snapshot of a data base rather than storing the huge data.

Data representation: As large number of restaurants could be found around current location/ hotel of stay; we need efficient data structure like decision tree. Each non leaf node of tree can be one of the template attribute (like rating, distance) and leaf nodes can be actual restaurants.

To create optimally homogeneous decision tree, we can use the disorder formula from information theory and apply it to each attribute of the template. Attribute that yields the minimum disorder can be picked as the root node.

$$\text{Average disorder} = \sum_b \left(\frac{n_b}{n_t} \right) \times \left(\sum_c - \frac{n_{bc}}{n_b} \log_2 \frac{n_{bc}}{n_b} \right),$$

where

- n_b is the number of samples in branch b ,
- n_t is the total number of samples in all branches,
- n_{bc} is the total of samples in branch b of class c .

**Above formula is taken from book 'Artificial Intelligence by Patrick Henry Winston, chapter 21'

Snapshot of example of decision tree is as below:

Once the decision tree is ready, we can convert it into set of rules in 'If Then' format. Path from root node till leaf can be put as 'if' clause and the actual leaf node can be put as 'then' clause. For above tree example, we can generate rules as below:

***If rating is good, price range is cheap, veg option is yes, distance is walkable
Then choose 'Restaurant1', 'Restaurant2'***

***If rating is bad
Then choose nothing***

If rating is good, price range is cheap, veg option is no

Then choose nothing

If no rule is applicable

Then choose nothing

Ratings field in template frame: As we can refer to multiple food review sites, there can be different ratings to the same restaurant. The web scrapper component should scrape not only the overall average rating but also negative comments about the important attributes to the user. For example, in my case, a restaurant with good ratings might have bad reviews about its veg dishes. Thus the AI agent should come up with its own rating algorithm and categorize the restaurant as 'good' or 'bad'.

Below is the flowchart of the application.

Finalizing options: Agent can choose decided number (5 or 10 etc.) of final restaurants from the many that might get filtered by decision tree. All chosen restaurants can be then proposed to the user and can be represented as ‘answer frames’ as below. Details about the restaurant can be easily pulled by web scrapper component using website’s developer APIs.

Slot	Value
Name	Panera Bread
Address	"..."
Phone	".."
isOpen	Yes

Timing	7 AM to 10 PM
Map	"..."
IsWalkable	Yes
Price Range	Cheap
Veg options	yes
Suggested dish for you	Broccoli cheddar soup
Feedback	
Problematic attributes	

Note that last two fields are empty and will be filled after receiving user feedback.

Challenge-3: How to keep learning?

It may happen that one of the suggested restaurants is visited by the user but still he/she does not like it. Thus, it is important to keep the the answer frames in memory until we receive feedback for each suggestion. If no feedback is given for long time, the frame instances can be discarded.

If the feedback is positive, agent knows that it is on right track. If feedback is negative, agent should ask questions about what went wrong. User can choose 'Problematic attributes' like 'rush hours', 'rude service', 'shabby ambience' etc.

AI agent thus knows that the user does care about more factors about restaurant selection than he thought initially. These new attributes should be part of the template frame and the decision tree for next cycle.

References:

** The logic is inspired by Author, Patrick Henry Winston (Third edition). Artificial intelligence, chapter 21, page 349.

** Web scrapper component can use developer's APIs from sites [Yelp API Link](#) and [TripAdvisor API](#)